

Table 1. Characteristics of the studies included in the review (N = 64)

Study	Country of Study*	Sample Size (N)	Study Approach	Is the study about the needs of pCC or YV/CG?	ML Aspects - Is access to media or technologies addressed?	ML Aspects - Is comprehension or understanding addressed?	ML Aspects - Is critical evaluation of information addressed?	ML Aspects - Is privacy addressed?	ML Aspects - Is communication in digital environments addressed?	ML Aspects - Is content creation addressed?	ML Aspects - Is participation and civic engagement addressed?	ML Aspects - Are mediation skills of caregivers or professionals addressed?	ML Aspects - Is autonomy in media use addressed?
(Ågren et al., 2020)	Sweden	922	Quantitative	YV/CG	Yes	Yes	No	No	Yes	No	No	Yes	Yes
(Alanazi et al., 2025)	Saudi Arabia	120	Mixed Methods	YV/CG	Yes	Yes	No	No	No	No	No	Yes	Yes
(Anapey et al., 2025)	Ghana	3307	Quantitative	YV/CG	Yes	No	No	No	No	No	No	Yes	Yes
(Anrijs et al., 2022)	Belgium	94	Quantitative	YV/CG	Yes	Yes	No	No	Yes	No	No	Yes	Yes
(Batz et al., 2022)	Germany	37	Quantitative	Both	Yes	No	No	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
(Bayor et al., 2018)	Australia	43	Mixed Methods	pCC	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
(Bosse et al., 2020)	Germany	24	Quantitative	pCC	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes
(Castilla et al., 2020)	Spain	28	Quantitative	pCC	Yes	Yes	No	No	No	No	No	Yes	Yes
(Caton & Landman, 2021)	United Kingdom	26	Qualitative	YV/CG	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No	Yes	Yes
(Chadwick & Buell, 2023)	United Kingdom	3	Qualitative	Both	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	No	No	Yes	Yes
(Chadwick et al. 2023)	United Kingdom	19	Qualitative	pCC	Yes	No	No	No	Yes	No	No	No	Yes
(Chaparro-Mantilla et al., 2021)	Colombia	30	Quantitative	pCC	Yes	No	No	No	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	No
(Chiner et al., 2019)	Spain	582	Quantitative	YV/CG	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No	Yes	Yes
(Chiner et al., 2022)	Spain	208	Quantitative	YV/CG	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No	No	No	Yes	Yes
(Chiner et al., 2024)	Chile	211	Quantitative	YV/CG	Yes	Yes	No	No	No	No	No	Yes	Yes
(Christiansen et al., 2020)	Sweden	20	Qualitative	pCC	Yes	Yes	No	No	Yes	No	No	No	Yes
(Christiansen et al., 2021)	Transnational Study	1082	Quantitative	pCC	Yes	Yes	No	No	No	No	No	No	Yes
(Damant et al., 2024)	United Kingdom	32	Qualitative	YV/CG	Yes	No	No	No	No	No	No	Yes	Yes
(Deng et al., 2025)	United States	8189	Qualitative	pCC	Yes	Yes	No	No	Yes	No	No	No	Yes
(Dequanter et al., 2022)	Belgium	24	Qualitative	Both	Yes	Yes	No	No	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes
(Engwall, 2022)	Sweden	17	Qualitative	YV/CG	Yes	No	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	No
(Gao et al., 2024)	China	16	Qualitative	Both	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes
(Heitplatz et al., 2020)	Germany	50	Qualitative	pCC	Yes	No	No	No	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes
(Heitplatz, 2020)	Germany	79	Qualitative	Both	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes
(Heponiemi et al., 2023)	Finland	1426	Quantitative	pCC	Yes	No	No	No	No	No	No	Yes	Yes
(Human et al., 2025)	South Africa	67	Mixed Methods	YV/CG	Yes	No	No	No	No	No	No	Yes	Yes
(Jakobsson et al., 2022)	Sweden	32	Quantitative	pCC	Yes	Yes	No	No	Yes	No	No	Yes	Yes
(Johansson & Engwall, 2026)	Sweden	19	Qualitative	YV/CG	Yes	No	No	No	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes
(Jørgensen et al., 2023)	Denmark	124	Quantitative	pCC	Yes	No	No	No	No	No	Yes	Yes	Yes
(Kärnä et al., 2022)	Transnational Study	520	Mixed Methods	Both	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
(Kumaş & Yildirim, 2024)	Turkey	180	Quantitative	YV/CG	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No	Yes	No
(Kurt et al., 2023)	Turkey	407	Quantitative	YV/CG	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No	Yes	Yes
(Lee et al., 2022)	South Korea	124	Mixed Methods	Unclear	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	No	No	No	Yes
(Li et al., 2025)	China	4270	Quantitative	Unclear	Yes	Yes	No	No	Yes	No	No	No	No
(Liu et al., 2023)	China	10325	Quantitative	Unclear	Yes	No	No	No	Yes	No	No	No	Yes
(MacMillan et al., 2020)	United Kingdom	104	Quantitative	YV/CG	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No	Yes	Yes
(MacMillan et al., 2022)	United Kingdom	14	Qualitative	pCC	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
(Ménard et al., 2025)	Canada	54	Qualitative	Unclear	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
(Menschik et al., 2024)	Germany	79	Mixed Methods	YV/CG	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes
(Mentis et al. 2020)	United States	20	Qualitative	Both	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No	Yes	Yes
(Middle & Welch, 2022)	United Kingdom	9	Qualitative	pCC	Yes	No	No	No	Yes	No	No	Yes	Yes
(Ngiam et al., 2022)	Singapore	138	Quantitative	pCC	Yes	Yes	No	No	Yes	No	No	Yes	Yes
(Nikken et al., 2024)	Netherlands	19	Qualitative	YV/CG	Yes	Yes	Yes	Partially	Yes	No	No	Yes	Yes
(Ong et al., 2025)	Malasya	27	Qualitative	Both	Yes	Yes	No	No	Yes	No	No	Yes	Yes

Study	Country of Study*	Sample Size (N)	Study Approach	Is the study about the needs of pCC or YV/CG?	ML Aspects - Is access to media or technologies addressed?	ML Aspects - Is comprehension or understanding addressed?	ML Aspects - Is critical evaluation of information addressed?	ML Aspects - Is privacy addressed?	ML Aspects - Is communication in digital environments addressed?	ML Aspects - Is content creation addressed?	ML Aspects - Is participation and civic engagement addressed?	ML Aspects - Are mediation skills of caregivers or professionals addressed?	ML Aspects - Is autonomy in media use addressed?
(Osuna et al., 2025)	United States	38	Mixed Methods	Both	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes
(Pan & Liu, 2026)	China	8349	Quantitative	pCC	Yes	Yes	No	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes
(Pérez-Rugosa et al., 2025)	Italy	334	Quantitative	pCC	Yes	No	No	No	No	No	Yes	No	Yes
(Rajagopal & Chandrashekar, 2024)	India	32	Mixed Methods	pCC	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes
(Safari et al., 2023)	Norway	15	Qualitative	Both	Yes	Yes	No	No	No	No	No	Yes	Yes
(Schloman et al., 2022)	Germany	21	Quantitative	pCC	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes
(Seok & DaCosta, 2016)	South Korea	352	Quantitative	pCC	Yes	Yes	No	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
(Setchell et al., 2020)	Australia	10	Qualitative	pCC	Yes	Yes	No	No	Yes	No	No	Partially	Yes
(Shin et al., 2022)	South Korea	1016	Quantitative	Unclear	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Partially	Yes
(Spencer et al., 2023)	United States	420	Quantitative	Both	Yes	Yes	No	No	Yes	No	No	Yes	No
(Sube & Bühler, 2022)	Germany	37	Qualitative	Both	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes
(Thirumanickam et al., 2024)	Australia	6	Mixed Methods	pCC	Yes	Yes	Partially	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes
(Tymoshchuk et al., 2022)	Portugal	78	Quantitative	pCC	Yes	Partially	No	No	Yes	Yes	No	Partially	Yes
(Wang et al., 2024)	Transnational Study	62,413	Quantitative	pCC	Yes	No	No	No	Yes	Yes	No	Partially	Yes
(Xin et al., 2025)	China	1016	Quantitative	pCC	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Partially	No	Partially	No	Yes
(Yurkewich et al., 2018)	Canada	12	Mixed Methods	pCC	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
(Zainal et al., 2025)	Singapore	30	Quantitative	YV/CG	Yes	Yes	Partially	No	Yes	No	Partially	Yes	Yes
(Zhang et al., 2025)	China	23	Qualitative	Both	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
(Zhu et al., 2024)	China	70	Qualitative	Both	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Partially	Yes	Yes
(Zhu et al., 2025)	China	20	Quantitative	pCC	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Partially	Yes